

Ultra-Wideband Portable MEMS FTIR Spectrometer towards the MIR Spectral Fingerprint Region

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Portable infrared spectral sensors are gaining importance for instant on-field analysis, eliminating the need to wait for samples to reach labs. Miniaturization of Fourier transform InfraRed (FTIR) spectrometers based on the Micro-Electro-Mechanical System (MEMS) technology has been proven to be one of the most promising approaches in this field of portable handheld spectrometers [1]. Most of the portable spectrometers are limited in wavelength range to the Near-InfraRed (NIR) where many technologies are validated [2]. However the widest reported spectral range for a MEMS FTIR spectrometers was 1470 cm^{-1} ($6.8\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) [3], which is on the edge of the fingerprint spectral region, one of the most important wavelength ranges for material identification [4].

In this work, we present an ultra-wideband portable MEMS FTIR spectrometer shown in Fig. 1 (a), which operates up to 1160 cm^{-1} ($8.6\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) in the Mid-InfraRed (MIR) extending the range to the fingerprint region beyond 1500 cm^{-1} for the first time. The core engine is a MEMS FTIR chip including a Michelson interferometer with one moving mirror driven by a micro comb-drive actuator as shown in the top left of Fig. 1 (a). All-silicon MEMS chips based on free-space propagation of light have the advantage of allowing operation in a very broadband spectral range without being impacted by the material dispersion of silicon as it is almost negligible in the MIR. In addition, the method used for light coupling to MEMS interferometer using a Micro-Optical Reflective Mirror (MORM) [5] enables such an ultra-wideband operation thanks to the all-reflective design, where the light does not propagate in a lens material. Moreover, the output is coupled, using an MORM, to an InAsSb cooled detector by Vigo Photonics [6] enabling the operation in the extended wavelength range.

The spectrometer is characterized using a silicon carbide light source measuring the transmission of a gas cell filled with carbon dioxide CO_2 , methane CH_4 , carbon monoxide CO and hydrogen sulfide H_2S in addition to another gas cell containing acetone $\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$ showing different absorption peaks in the MIR range as shown in top of Fig. 1 (b). Also, several thin film filters at different wavelengths, covering the range of interest, are measured and overlaid on the same graph showing the wavelength range extension up to 1160 cm^{-1} . By extending the MEMS comb-drive actuator travel range, all measurements were repeated at 50 cm^{-1} resolution showing better distinguishing/resolving the close peaks as shown in the bottom of Fig. 1 (b).

Fig. 1. Portable MEMS FTIR Spectrometer schematic in (a) and measured gases and filters spectra in (b) at two different spectral resolutions of 66 and 50 cm^{-1} .

References

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- [6] InAsSb superlattice four-stage thermoelectrically-cooled optically immersed photovoltaic infrared detectors (<https://vigophotonics.com/product/pvia-4te-10-1x1-to8-wznsear-36/>).